

THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF PSYCHOPEDAGOGY TO PLAY ACTIVITIES IN THE SCHOOL CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

Psychopedagogy covers knowledge in psychology and pedagogy. In this sense, this research has as main objective to present the contributions of psychopedagogy in the school context. For the development of this study, an exploratory and descriptive bibliographic search was carried out, based on data from scientific articles, published in Google Scholar, searches registered in the SCIELO, VHL databases, and not exhausting searches, were still research in digital magazines. In this sense, the conceptual framework proposed in this article is necessary, as it offers a meaning, a concept that facilitates the understanding of the theme of this study. Therefore, the present study brings as a theoretical framework the assumptions of authors who carried out studies on the importance of male presence in family planning actions. Based on the studies carried out, it can be seen that psychopedagogy emerged with the objective of helping people with learning problems. In this sense, the results of this research show that psychopedagogy is concerned with understanding the cognitive, emotional, social, cultural, physical and pedagogical processes of the student who, in some way, suffers from problems in the teaching-learning process. In order to meet the objective proposed by this study, it was possible to present pertinent information on the role of the psychopedagogue in the context of public education.

Keywords: Teaching learning. Psychopedagogue. Education.

INTRODUCTION

Psychopedagogy encompasses knowledge from two distinct areas; but, Psychology and Pedagogy overlap. In this sense, this research aims to present the contributions of psychopedagogy in the school context. Given the difficulties of understanding and the

motivations that encourage human thought towards learning, the fusion of empirical knowledge from the two epistemological fields highlighted above allows education professionals to get as close as possible to practical solutions when confronting issues arise. conflict situations in the classroom and even with the aim of improving their respective practices.

Faced with the problem raised, this work is based on the search for empirically based answers by renowned authors, who carried out studies on the topic addressed. Thus, the hypothesis raised here consists of the contributions that the psychopedagogue's work makes in the school context, given that his actions aim to improve the quality of the learning process.

The development of research in the psychopedagogical field is due, in particular, to advances in the discovery of Psychoanalysis and its interpretation in order to understand how children's thoughts are interpreted, a situation that begins with the studies of Freud (1856-1939) and which unfold in the works of Anna Freud, Wallon, Piaget, Vygotsky, Lacan. It was, based on the intense studies carried out in the field of early childhood education and the intellectual development of children, by such scholars that Psychopedagogy could create its own research framework, producing, from its own inductions and deductions, a profound interpretation of the psychology of the target object of your intervention.

From this, you can develop your own working methods, working in prophylaxis, therapy, clinics, institutions, always providing broad and deep interpretations about the problems and issues that permeate human, epistemic and empirical educational training. Its application in the educational context is due to the fact that it applies, in its interpretations, the principle of reasonableness and that, the symptoms presented of difficulties related to learning do not always have a pathological origin, and may be a mere biological action manifested in a *sui generis way* in each individual.

This research is justified by the need to understand the contributions of psychopedagogy in the school context. From this perspective, the relevance of this study lies in the presentation of information that contributes to the understanding of the role of the educational psychologist in this context.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF PSYCHOPEDAGOGY

Psychopedagogy emerged with the aim of helping individuals who present problems in the context of learning, and its areas of activity are mainly “in preventive actions in institutions and in the clinic with individualized care” (BOSSA, 2011, p. 48).

It works in a propaedeutic line based on medical and psychological knowledge and, also, seeking to provide therapeutic services that prove to be efficient in solving problems related to learning. Therefore, Psychopedagogy strives to search for plausible answers to conflicts that concern the learning process with work techniques that can be carried out individually or in groups, aiming to rescue the interest in learning, so that it is possible to observe which Factors can probably contribute or not to the teaching process being efficient and effective.

According to Visca (2007), the emergence of Psychopedagogy in the educational sphere

It was a subsidiary action of medicine and psychology; it was characterized as an independent and complementary knowledge, possessing an object of study, the learning process and its own diagnostic, corrective and preventive resources (VISCA, 2007, p. 23).

This means that Psychopedagogy is understood as an autonomous science, even though it seeks much of its knowledge from studies carried out by other sciences. However, its framework for understanding the causes and symptoms of problems related to learning, highlighting the field of children and adolescents, has put it in a position to act to solve numerous problems in the cognitive field.

Its application in the educational field is linked to the process in which human beings, nowadays, spend their entire childhood and adolescence immersed in the school environment. It is natural that many of the conflicts that would be experienced within the family, with parents, siblings and other relatives manifest themselves there, in relation to people who are strangers to them, by nature; but not for coexistence. This has been an expensive chapter for Psychopedagogy, because many have not yet understood that the family environment and the people who are part of it are already foreign to the child and to everyone involved in the process, because it is an absolute contrast to the phylogenetic aspect of the human species.

Bossa (2007) highlights that, “psychopedagogy, as a production of scientific knowledge, was born from the need for a better understanding of the learning process, not being enough as an application of psychology to pedagogy” (p.19).

This statement clarifies that psychological action on learning processes is not sufficient, because its study condition is focused on problems linked to the brain and behavior, with little space for the sociological analyzes that make up human existence, especially, when referring to childhood, a developmental phase that is greatly influenced by the parents' living conditions, sometimes marked by states of symbolic violence and conflicts that are far beyond the child's understanding and that end up interfering in the child's emotional, transforming into fear and insecurity. All of this has a negative impact on learning, because children living in the midst of

parental conflict are not bound by the parameters for assimilating content, given that their concern is to stay safe.

In this sense, Psychopedagogy will seek to delve deeper into this aspect related to which external element is awakening a trigger that prevents the child from advancing and developing in the cognitive field. As it is a science that has its line of scientific investigation based on pedagogical knowledge and didactic principles, the professional's action becomes broader and more likely to find a plausible answer relevant to the cognitive problem in question that the child presents and that the pedagogical interventions prepared by the teacher are not presenting the expected results.

The objectives of Psychopedagogy applied to problems related to learning are not to solve the situation itself, purely to advance the process. Each case is studied, in detail, so that, through its systematic study, others are clarified and, also, that light can be shed on situations that appear to be obscure and difficult to empirically understand about the elements that make up human learning. . In this way, each case becomes a path that allows us to understand other clinical-pedagogical situations when placed under careful technical analysis.

According to Bossa (2000, p. 21):

Psychopedagogy studies the characteristics of human learning: how we learn, how this learning varies evolutionarily and is conditioned by various factors, how changes in learning occur, how to recognize, treat and prevent them.

In the 1960s and 1970s, the theoretical currents of Behaviorism and Humanism made use of Psychopedagogy. Thus, Behaviorism had stimulus and response as an essential part, while Humanism proposed doing the will of the learning being. Santos (2009) highlights that, in 1970, the first courses aimed at specializing in psychopedagogy emerged in Brazil, aiming to complement the training of psychologists and educators who sought to solve certain problems. Such courses were structured based on scientific knowledge and within a historical context.

Another important fact in the history of psychopedagogy was the first meeting of psychopedagogy in SP, in November 1984, with Clarissa Golbert and Sônia Kiguel, who presented works aimed at the activities of psychopedagogues in Porto Alegre. From this event, the Free Group of Studies in Psychopedagogy (as it was called) was founded, now it became the Association of Psychopedagogues with the aim of discussing psychopedagogical issues monthly (SANTOS, 2009, p. 17 and 18).

From the moment that problems related to learning and cognitive development begin to be discussed in assemblies formed by specialists interested in delving deeper into the topics

and, therefore, expanding the domain over the contents, symptoms and causes, much is achieved in terms of to scientific production capable of guiding the empirical work of teachers and pedagogues, in schools, as well as parents, in their homes and in caring for children.

What this group intended was for the problems presented by teachers, regarding what was happening in the classroom, to be transformed into technical study material, providing scientific learning about the problem situations experienced, thus transforming them into analytical didactic experiences.

Weiss (1991, p. 15), highlights that:

There are different approaches to what is meant by psychopedagogy at school. I will adopt the position of considering it as work that seeks to improve relationships with learning, as well as better quality in the construction of students' and educators' own learning. And giving the teacher and student a level of autonomy in the search for knowledge and, at the same time, enabling a critical stance in relation to the structure of the school and the society it represents. For this, it is necessary to have a position on what the school reproduces.

In this way, the educational psychologist carries out detailed and comprehensive work, therefore, it is not work that takes place in isolation. As it investigates the life history of its patients, considering access to the child's parents/guardians and the school institution attended, it proposes activities that aim to identify the main difficulties. From this perspective, an accurate diagnosis and subsequently a qualitative intervention throughout the teaching-learning process becomes possible. Thus, there is a need to develop different actions, as evidenced by Bossa (1994), in which he argues that,

For the Psychopedagogue, learning is a process that involves putting into action different systems that intervene in the entire subject: the network of relationships and cultural and language codes that, from before birth, take place in each human being as he or she develops. incorporates society (Id., p. 51).

It is worth noting that one of the main objectives of Psychopedagogy, initially, was to investigate issues related to the learning or non-learning of some children. Gasparian (1997, p.15), states that “for a long period, the child was attributed with pathology for not learning; Thus, in Europe, in the 19th century, doctors, pedagogues and psychiatrists raised questions about non-learning, among them: Maria Montessori, Decroly and Janine”.

It turns out that *not-learning* came to be understood by such professionals as a consequence, as a symptom that hid a deeper and unknown cause, for which there was still no plausible explanation and everything that could be observed through experience with children

in hospitals, orphanages and other non-educational institutions, demonstrated that regular schools needed guidance regarding the application of their didactic-pedagogical procedures and the verification of results, taking these as means for case studies and not simply for classification made by iron and fire, producing two distinct groups in the classes: the intelligent, condemned to success and the backward, condemned to imminent failure.

Regarding institutional psychopedagogy, Veras (2015) points out that:

By proposing that institutional psychopedagogy be present both in thinking about school practices and in their application, it is also proposing to think about micro relationships within the educational context. In this way, the encouragement of stimulating educational environments meets the action of institutional psychopedagogy and the understanding that public policies must highlight in their practices the place of power of minorities (VERAS, 2015, p. 80).

Based on the above, it is understood that psychopedagogy emerged considering the need to help people who have learning problems. Thus, the role of the psychopedagogue in the school context becomes essential.

THE ROLE OF THE PSYCHOPEDAGOGIST IN THE SCHOOL CONTEXT

It is known that the educational psychologist plays a fundamental role in the teaching process. According to Bossa (1994), "thinking about school in the light of Psychopedagogy means analyzing a process that includes methodological, relational and socio-cultural issues, encompassing the point of view of those who teach and those who learn, encompassing the participation of the family and the society".

This extends beyond the classroom, as the professional begins to look for possible causes that could explain the problem raised, based on the analysis of cases. As soon as,

There are different levels of action. First, the educational psychologist works in educational processes with the aim of reducing the frequency of learning problems. Its work focuses on didactic-methodological issues, as well as the training and guidance of teachers, in addition to providing advice to parents. In the second action, the objective is to reduce and address existing learning problems. To this end, a diagnostic plan is created, from which we try to evaluate the curricula with teachers, so that the disorder does not reoccur, we are preventing the appearance of others (BOSSA, 1994, p. 102).

This statement reiterates the thought already stated above, that the study of cases presented by parents and teachers and their consequent solution creates opportunities to face new situations; not being able to confuse what is achieved, in terms of knowledge, with the

ability to understand any and all future cases, because this is foolishness. Each case must be treated as a special case and recorded, in detail, from its appearance, the investigation and its possible conclusion and empirical developments.

Barbosa (2001) states that psychopedagogical action within the team or institution, to be effective, needs to interpret different roles played, the way in which they were assigned and assumed, as well as the perspectives that are latent in this movement of assigning and accepting the role .

Bossa (2007) argues that psychopedagogical action basically takes place in different clinical and institutional contexts, and in the field of scientific research. Therefore, psychopedagogy is concerned with understanding the processes related to cognition, emotion, social, cultural, physical and pedagogical of the student who, in some way, suffers from learning difficulties. And, its intervention aims to include parents/guardians in the educational process, through meetings, thus enabling the monitoring of work with the school team. Therefore, in the psychopedagogue's view, parents/guardians should occupy a large space in the school context, giving their opinion and participating.

Kiguel (1983) highlights that psychopedagogy is in the process of organizing a specific theoretical body, considering the integration of pedagogical, psychological, speech therapy, neuropsychological and psycholinguistic sciences to understand the phenomenon of learning.

PSYCHOPEDAGOGY AND ITS CONTRIBUTIONS, THROUGH PLAY, TO PEDAGOGICAL WORK

Considering the practice of playful activities in psychopedagogy, it can be said that it helps students achieve their best performance. However, activities alone do not solve all problems related to the educational process, they can help promote significant changes.

According to Fagali and Vale (2009, p. 35):

Thinking about school in the light of Psychopedagogy implies focusing especially on teacher training. Teacher training proposals must offer the teacher the conditions to establish a mature and healthy relationship with their students, parents and school authorities. Investigating, analyzing and making proposals for teacher training that considers these aspects constitutes an extremely important task, which Psychopedagogy is responsible for.

From this perspective, psychopedagogy plays an important role in the educational context, which guarantees the student the necessary and unique time for their learning and the space necessary for this. The idea of professional training for the teaching field is a discourse

that has been lost, because it always presents the search for a super teacher, capable of avoiding the appearance of any cognitive problems and even their quick solution, when they appear, through his teaching, denying any and all interference outside his condition.

Marcelino (1996, p. 38) argues that, “it is essential that the child is provided with time and space so that the playful nature of leisure can be experienced with intensity capable of forming a solid basis for creativity and cultural participation”.

Playfulness is a resource widely used in psychopedagogical clinics, in which the behavior of students in relation to objects is observed, whether they are of a pedagogical nature or not. What we are looking for are the causes of unsatisfactory performance in the classroom. According to Weiss (2004), the playful space during diagnosis brings the possibility of a better understanding of the learner's real situation and level of development. Psychopedagogical intervention must explore pedagogical games, as playing is universal and breaks the boundaries between diagnosis and treatment, since the diagnosis itself becomes therapeutic in nature.

With regard to learning potential, Antunes (2003) reveals that,

Two children, at the same age, have the same intelligence window with the same level of opening, this does not mean, however, that they are equal; The genetic history of each person can make the effect of stimuli on this opening greater or lesser, producing a more immediate or slower effect. It is a mistake to assume that the stimulus can make the window open faster. Therefore, this opening needs to be used by parents and teachers with balance, serenity and patience. The stimulus does not act directly on the window, but, if applied appropriately, it develops skills and these, yes, lead to significant learning (Id., p. 19).

In view of the above, it is understood that it is essential that children are stimulated from an early age, as each child has a different rhythm and ways of learning. Therefore, it is interesting to observe the skills and potential of each one, and provide dynamic interventions, exploring the individual skills of the learners.

As long as they are stimulated from a very early age, it should be noted that the environment should provide such situations and not adults, directly. Many parents have destroyed their children and turned them into true freaks, precisely because they believe they are capable of creating such prodigies through opportunities imposed on them. Therefore, it should be clarified that,

Parents play an important role in the process of developing autonomy. If they encourage the child's initiatives, praise success, give tasks that do not exceed the child's capabilities, are consistent in their demands and accept failures, they will be contributing to the emergence of a feeling of self-confidence and self-esteem (SABINI, 1998, p. 65).

Therefore, it is understood that psychopedagogy brings many contributions to work with recreational activities, as it helps in the teaching-learning process of students, especially those who have difficulties learning.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Based on the studies carried out, it can be seen that psychopedagogy emerged with the aim of helping people who have learning problems. In this sense, the results of this research indicate that psychopedagogy is concerned with understanding the cognitive, emotional, social, cultural, physical and pedagogical processes of the student who, in some way, suffers from problems in the teaching-learning process.

The considerations made throughout this study show that the educational psychologist plays a fundamental role in the teaching process. In line with the objective of this study, it was possible to present pertinent information about the role of the educational psychologist in the context of public education. Thus, the importance of the presence of this professional in school planning actions stands out, taking into account what scholars say on the subject. Therefore, it is understood that there is a need for reflection and, mainly, on contributions.

Through the present study it was possible to see that at school, the psychopedagogue assumes great relevance, as he promotes the stimulation of the development of interpersonal relationships, the establishment of bonds, the use of teaching methods compatible with the most recent conceptions regarding this process.

It was also possible to realize that the psychopedagogue is the professional indicated to advise and guide the school, mainly with regard to the different aspects of the teaching-learning process, thus acting in a preventive manner. In this way, the psychopedagogue assumes an important mission, that of being supportive with regard to the learning process, mediating information and indicating possible paths to be taken by the subject, without, however, imposing any conditions on them.

Therefore, the Psychopedagogy professional proposes and assists in the development of projects favorable to educational changes, aiming at the discovery and development of the child's capabilities, as well as contributing to students being able to look at this world in which they live by knowing how to interpret it and be able to interfere with it safely and competently.

As explained above, the psychopedagogue assumes the role of working in a preventive manner to detect learning difficulties, as well as developing a diagnosis and working together with the family in the face of occurrences arising from difficulties in the learning process.

Therefore, it is essential to consider the relevant aspects in the student's life, as well as the establishment of bonds.

This study also opens up perspectives for new research, in order to verify the lack of knowledge about the contributions of psychopedagogy to playful activities in the school context.

REFERENCES

ALMEIDA, Paulo Nunes de. *Playful education : pedagogical techniques and games*. 5. Ed. São Paulo: Loyola, 2003.

ANTUNES, Celso. *The game and the childish education*. São Paulo: Voices, 2003.

BARBOSA, LMS *Psychopedagogy within the educational institution*. Curitiba: Exponent; 2001.

BOSSA, Nadia A. *Psychopedagogy in Brazil: contributions from the practice*. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2007.

BOSSA, NA *Psychopedagogy in Brazil: contributions from practice*. Porto Alegre: Medical Arts; 1994.

FAGALI, EQ; VALE, Zélia Del Rio do. *Applied institutional psychopedagogy: dynamic school learning and construction in the classroom*. 10 ed. Petrópolis: Voices, 2009.

GASPARIAN, Maria Cecília Castro. *Contributions of the systemic relational model to institutional psychopedagogy*. São Paulo: Lemos Editorial, 1997.

MARCELINO, Nelson Carvalho. *Leisure studies: an introduction*. Campinas: Associated Authors, 1996.

MARTINI, ML *Psychopedagogy: Some theoretical and practical considerations*. Available at: <
<http://site.unitau.br/scripts/prppg/humanas/download/psicopedagogia-N1-1999.pdf> >. Accessed on January 4, 2020.

SANTOS, Denise Moreira dos. *How psychopedagogy can contribute to the treatment of autistic children*. Available at: https://www.avm.edu.br/docpdf/monografias_publicadas/T205038.pdf. Accessed on January 8, 2020.

VERAS, NCO . *Institutional Psychopedagogy and Deaf Education in Brazil, possible meetings*. Education, arts and inclusion. Vol. 11, no. 1, 2015.

VISCA, J. *Psychopedagogical clinic: Convergent epistemology*. 5. Ed. Porto Alegre: Artes Médicas, 2006.

WEISS, Maria Lucia Lemme. *Clinical psychopedagogy: a diagnostic view of school learning problems*. Rio de Janeiro: DP & A, 2004.